

Lack of Familial Love and Affection in Sashi Deshpande's *The Dark Holds No Terrors*

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Abstract

*This paper studies the novel *The Dark Holds No Terrors*, where Sashi Deshpande explains, how a deserted attitude is kept for a girl child by her own parents and how that girl becomes a psychiatric patient and permanent sufferer till coming over by own declaration. Novel presents the suffocating feeling of a girl, who never gets love from her parents and looks marriage as a heaven on the earth, but after marriage she finds dichotomy between her prospect and reality. It is a story of internal and external distressing experiences of a middle-class educated working woman, who is a famous physician and working person. Her dichotomy breaks out with self-realization and conflicts the entire situation. She takes a lengthy expedition painfully with sour experiences to come over this situation.*

Keywords: Suffocate, annihilated, petrified, patriarchy, mirage.

Shashi Deshpande is an Indian novelist who was born in 1938 in Karnataka and educated in Bombay and Bangalore. Deshpande has written four children's books, a number of short stories, and nine novels, besides several perceptive essays, available in a volume entitled *Writing from the Margin and Other Essays*. Her first novel, *The Dark Holds No Terrors*, was published in 1980. In most of her works Sashi Deshpande depicts the piteous state of women.

God has created everything in this world in a beautiful manner. God's every creation in this world has its own significance. He created everything such as plants, animals, birds and many other things in this world. But those creatures were not created according to the resemblance of God. Think how God has love upon the human beings. But God is really upset with present evils in this society. God not only creates a man, he also creates a women companion for the man from his own bone. Every religious scripture praises the wife, the women and they don't consider them as inferior.

In Bible when Salomon writes about a "virtuous wife", he comments like this: "For her worth is far above rubies" (Proverbs 31:10). Quran says like this "Women shall with justice similar to exercised against them (men)" (Quran 2:228). Lord Krishna Says, "Men can achieve purity, prosperity, grace, fame, glory, endurance, patience and intelligence through women". Thus all religions provide a significant

place for women. But in practical life the real state of women is very different and pathetic. Women are considered and treated submissive and inferior in the society. They are denied of their own rights. They are harassed and abused. They are considered only as an object and a toy for pleasure. No one understands her own feeling and emotions. Even in much Family the treatment between boy and girl is different.

In this novel “Dark Holds No Terrors”, Sashi Deshpande depicts how the tender heart of Saru longs for love and care from her parents. Saru is projected as a victim of childhood uncertainty. Parental love is essential for the development of a child, but Saru lacks it. She has no kind word or word of appreciation and affection for her father or mother. The father is a sign of apathy indifference. Saru has no word of honour for her mother. As long as the mother is alive, there is no love and affection between among mother and daughter. She is unable to put-up with the mother’s excessive fondness shown towards her brother. She feels envious of her brother to see him receiving all the parental care and consideration. Her mother is a kind of woman who believes a girl to be a legal responsibility and a boy an asset. Here, to her mother, the boy is more significant than the girl. Her father takes least interest in her studies or development. His dissimilarity can be analyzed as an oblique expression of patriarchy that is emotionally harmful. She is not given any significance. No parental love and care is poured on her.

Saru is the main character of this novel, who married Manohar against her parents’ wish. So she leaves her home has no contact with her parents. When Saru returns to her parents’ home after the dispute with her husband she feels that many things have changed in her home. Her father smiles at her for the first time, which is a different act towards her. Saru mentions that, “He gave her a smile. The first smile she had for him” (18). But her father’s first smile was not a replica of his love and affection; it is only a way of apologizing to Saru for not putting up his dead wife’s photograph. This shows the relationship between Saru and her father. From this we can understand that she doesn’t enjoy the shade of her father’s love. She feels that after the death of her mother, her father has changed completely. Before her mother’s death her father doesn’t bother about the family activity. It is said,

During Saru’s childhood days she doesn’t have much attachment with her father, like Dhruva. Saru longs for her father’s love. “It had been Dhruva sitting on Baba’s lap and talking to him. And I thought ... I must show Baba something, anything to take his attention away from Dhruva sitting on his lap. I must, make him listen to me, no to Dhruva. I must make him ignore Dhruva”. (32)

Saru thinks that her father must ignore her brother. This shows that how much she was denied , avoided and uncared by her parents for the only reason of being a ‘girl child’. This makes the little soft heart of Saru suffocate. When Saru finds Madhav talking with Saru’s father about his college activities she feels for that because her father never asks her in her childhood about her school or college activities. She says, “He never took any interest in my school or college. He left it all to her. And she never really cared. Not after Dhruva’s death. I died long before I left home” (32). Her mother hurts her more when her brother Dhruva died. Her mother says, “Why didn’t you die? Why are you alive and he dead?” (34). This shows how indifferent her parents are with her.

When Saru is arranging the things in the cupboard she finds a bundle of photographs. She searches for her individual photograph but fails to find any of that. But she is able to find a photo of her, but it is not an individual one. It is the photo taken with her brother Dhruva. She feels for that and thinks she is annihilated. It is said, “There was no photograph of herself, she noticed without emotion. As if she had indeed been annihilated” (59).

When Madhav asks Saru to keep her mother's sari with herself she replies abruptly that she doesn't have any good memories of her mother: "I don't have any good memories of my mother" (59). This shows the improper relationship between Saru and her mother. Each and every child is beautiful and special to its mother.

Every mother considers her own daughter or son as princess or prince. But Saru's mother is an exceptional case. She tells to her own daughter that she is very ugly and she won't be good-looking even in her future: "You will never be good looking"(61). This shows the ruthless character of her mother.

She also hurts Saru for her dark complexion. It shows the cruel nature of her mother. She doesn't have soft corner for Saru in her heart. After the death of Dhruva, Saru is taken by Mashvi, a neighbour. Mashvi cares Saru very much; she plaited her hair with lots of love and care. After few days Saru's mother asks Saru to return home, but Saru is not ready to go home. She says, "I don't want to go. Not today" (74). Through this incident we can understand the tender heart of Saru, who is longing for affection from her parents.

Saru's choice of marriage is a comfort against the resentment of her parents. The slackness of mother, indifference of father and the burden of the guilt of the death of brother, forced Saru to depart her parental home and to seek spaces in professional life. The shade of the brutality of her mother, who emits her off from the family and let her stroll in void with her own deserted fate, makes her restless. The fear of being betrayed or being discarded remains rooted in her notice. Saru leaves her parental home influenced by the romantic fancy of Manohar who says, "When we're together, its heaven, wherever we are" (38).

After marriage Saru enjoys better economic and social status and also enjoys a pleasant-sounding relationship as Monohar's wife but after she becomes a lady doctor, equation changes. Both Manohar and Saru travel not only in different directions but even in opposite directions. In everything, be it intellect or occupation or success or ambition she surpasses her husband. Slowly Saru's social and economic status grows far beyond those of her husband. She is a demanding successful doctor in difference to Manu who is an under-salaried lecturer in a third rate college. She establishes herself as a career woman, and her job satisfies her ego, but this brings her no gladness at home.

Manohar's sense of inferiority changes him into a sadist, who gets pleasure by insulting his wife, harassing and, hurting her sexuality. She is two persons in one woman; she is a successful doctor during day time and a terrible petrified trapped animal at night. The sour understanding dawns upon her that the idea of the concept of love in marriage is a mirage, and an delusion. She considers that marriage is nothing and says,

Love... There was no such thing between man and woman.
There was only a need which both fought against, futilely,
the very futility turning into the thing they called 'love'.
It's only a word, she thought. Take away the word, the idea,
and the concept will wither away (72).

The only reason for her love affair is the lack of parental love and affection. Thus Sashi beautifully depicts the various state of Saru who longs for love, care and affection in her work *The Dark Holds No Terror*.

Work Cited

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